

Keywords:

#Persistent Identifier, #Interoperability,
#Metadata, #FAIR, #RDM #OpenScience,
#EOSCinPractice #RDA

In Vitro Veritas: data and metadata interoperability for physical samples

Leveraging the new IGSN (International Generic Sample Number) ID provided by DataCite in a research tool.

The EOSCFuture.eu/RDA open calls

The open calls managed by the Research Data Alliance (RDA) with funding from EOSCFuture.eu aim to bring data initiatives closer to EOSC and provide EOSC with expertise, tools, best practices, and standards from the global research data community, with a total million Euro reserved to fund over 65 grantees over 12 open calls.

The Project Involved

The Project was supported under the RDA Open Call for Interoperability Framework Contributions and implemented by Research Space (RSpace) and DataCite from December 2022 until July 2023. RSpace provided the digital research platform, which features an integrated electronic lab notebook and sample management system that are connected to an ecosystem of tools & services that researchers and data librarians commonly use. DataCite connects research outputs and resources with metadata—from samples and images to data and preprints - and facilitates the creation and management of persistent identifiers (PIDs), integrates services to improve research workflows, and facilitates the discovery and reuse of research outputs and resources.

The key objective of the project was to provide guiding principles for implementing persistent identification and metadata features on research tools to boost interoperability of research data and to support sample management workflows.

The project focused on building interoperability in research tools using IGSN DOIs provided by [DataCite](#), and the [RSpace digital research platform](#), as a case study.

The project work was closely related to the work being done by the RDA Working with PIDs in Tools IG. 50% of the IG co-chairs were involved in the project. A presentation of the project will be made at the joint Working with PIDs in Tools IG and National PIDs Strategies WG session at Plenary21, and the Working with PIDs in Tools IG will consider adopting the project report as an IG output.

Rory Macneil

CEO of Research Space, UK, host of the FAIR Data Podcast

Xiaoli Chen

Project Lead at DataCite

“The funding provided gave the opportunity to enhance interoperability in research data management, guided by the implementation of persistent identification and metadata features utilizing IGSN DOIs from DataCite and the RSpace digital research platform to create seamless data exchange and support streamlined sample management workflows”

The Research Community

Multiple scientific research domains which use tools to create, collect, manage, analyze, store and share research data and documents were involved. E.g., biology, chemistry, ecology, geology, environmental science, and engineering.

The Challenge

Lack of interoperability between tools/e-infrastructures hinders streamlining processes throughout the research lifecycle. It hampers research data and metadata collection and limits the scope for passing this data and metadata on to and from data repositories.

This issue is particularly acute when dealing with data and metadata for physical samples, which presents challenges at two levels. First, creating, collecting, and managing data related to the samples requires carefully designed software with a rich feature set which is flexible enough to address multiple kinds of workflows, yet intuitive for users. Second, sample management tools currently lack support for associating sample data with both ontologies and PIDs metadata.

Keywords:

#data, #OpenScience, #FAIRprinciples, #FAIRsharing, #FAIRdata #Trust, #FAIR indicators, #EOSCinPractice

Useful tips & tricks

The following tips are for research providers who are looking to integrate PIDs workflows into their platforms.

Select appropriate research institutions and researchers to engage with. Gather feedback and requirements from institutions and researchers as part of an iterative process. Consult widely with people with relevant and expert knowledge of the infrastructures and workflows being addressed, inside and outside your organization(s). When translating requirements into product design, start with a long list and refine this into a practical, doable minimum proof of concept to start with.

Benefits and impact

The ability to associate IGSNS with sample data has a potentially revolutionary impact on the discoverability of sample data, bringing a range of benefits, including wider dissemination of sample data, conducting more effective experiments, reproducibility of research, and knowledge generation. This benefit extends to the individual researchers and groups who conduct research involving physical samples, and also the institutions they work for. It will also extend to researchers and institutions who were not involved in the work but who will be able to more easily discover information about samples and the experiments they were used in, which will be useful in their own research.

Why do I need RDA?

Representatives of both organisations involved in this project are very active in the RDA, serving as co-chairs and members of many working groups and interest groups, attending Plenaries and presenting at sessions, and in other ways. The group activities and the plenaries provide a critical avenue for learning about important trends in research data management and meeting and engaging with stakeholders of the community, and shape policy and practice. No other research data organization has the breadth of engagement and participation, the depth of knowledge, or the sustained and regular activity of the RDA which is a unique and invaluable resource.

Useful material related to this story

rda-alliance.org

Why do I need EOSC?

EOSC funding was instrumental in making this research possible, and the feedback received in the early stage of the process was useful, e.g., we decided to focus only on IGSNS rather than PIDS more generally, which would not have been achievable in the short time available. The encouragement we received and the opportunity to present and discuss progress was also very helpful.

Across disciplines

Association of IGSNS with physical samples collected in multiple domains enables wider discovery of sample data between domains, resulting in more opportunities for cross-disciplinary data comparison and experimental exploration.

EOSC service or tool used

The EOSCFuture.eu/RDA grant provided the opportunity for DataCite and RSpace to team up to address the challenge of data and metadata interoperability for physical samples. It obliged the team to set up a specific work programme, and to work to a specified timeline. Further, regular EOSC-RDA group meetings were held during the project giving us insights and guidance on how to take this forward and how to narrow our focus to make the objectives we set achievable.

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